

**Studies on Some Biologically Active
Quinazolones. Synthesis of 2-phenoxy
methyl-3-N-substituted Amino Carbonyl
methyl-8-substituted 4(3H) quinazolones
as Anticonvulsant Agents**

J. S. SHUKLA, SHRADHA SAXENA and RANJANA MISRA
Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007
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QUINAZOLONES and their derivatives have drawn attention because of their prodigious range of activity e. g., CNS depressant¹, hypnotic², anti-convulsant^{3,4}, M.A.O. inhibitory⁵, etc. In the present paper we have described the synthesis of newer quinazolone derivatives with a view of getting enhanced anticonvulsant activity.

Substituted 4H-3,1 benzoxazines⁶ (III) were synthesised by the cyclization of substituted phenoxy acetyl chlorides⁷ with substituted anthranilic acids in pyridine. The compound III on condensation with glycine gave 2-phenoxy methyl-3-carboxymethyl-8-substituted 4(3H) quinazolones (IV). Acid chloride of (IV) on condensation with different amines in dry benzene and pyridine gave the desired product 2-phenoxy methyl-3-N substituted amino carbonyl methyl-8-substituted 4(3H) quinazolones (V).

Scheme I

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 137 spectrophotometer in KBr.

2-(o-Methyl phenoxy methyl)-3-carboxymethyl-8-iodo-(3H)-4-quinazolones: 2-(o-Methyl phenoxy methyl)-8-iodo anthranil (3.93 g; 0.01 mole) and glycine (0.8 g; 0.01 mole) were taken in 2:1 pyridine water mixture (30 ml) and refluxed on wire gauge for 5-6 hr. The solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was digested with 4 N HCl (100 ml) on a steam bath for 2-3 hr. The solid mass thus separated was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. m.p. 257°, yield 2.69 g (57%). IR (KBr) ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1695 (COOH), 1230 (C-O-C), 1660 (N-C=O) and 1610 (C=N).

Anal. Found: C, 47.64; H, 3.13; N, 6.01. $C_{17}H_{15}N_3O_4I$ requires C, 48; H, 3.3; N, 6.02%. Other compounds of this series were similarly prepared and the results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(SUBSTITUTED)PHENOXY METHYL-3-CARBOXYMETHYL-8-SUBSTITUTED-4-QUINAZOLONE (IV)

Compd.* No.	R	R ₁	m.p. °C	Molecular formula
Ia	H	H	209	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₄
Ib	H	o-Cl	218	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₄ Cl
Ic	H	o-OCH ₃	221	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄
Id	H	p-CH ₃	199	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄
Ie	I	H	248	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ I

* The compounds were obtained in about 66-70% yields. Elemental analyses of C, H and N were consistent.

2-(o-Methyl phenoxy methyl)-3-N-morpholinyl carbonyl methyl-8-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolone: A mixture of IV (2.25 g; 0.005 mole) and thionyl chloride (1.19 g; 0.01 mole) was refluxed in dry benzene (35 ml) for 5-6 hr. Excess of benzene was distilled under reduced pressure and morpholine (0.48 g; 0.005 mole) in pyridine (30 ml) added to the reaction mixture. The solution was refluxed for 2 hr. Excess of pyridine was removed and the residue poured in dil HCl and kept overnight. The solid thus separated was crystallised from ethanol to give V, m.p. 162°, yield 1.36 g (50%). Anal. Found: C, 50.52; H, 4.054; N, 8.01%. $C_{22}H_{21}N_5O_4I$ requires C, 50.91; H, 4.108%; N, 8.108%. IR (KBr) ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 1630 (CON), 1670 (C-N). NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 7.77 (d, 1H, J=8Hz, C₅-H), 7.31 (t, 1H, J=8Hz, C₆-H), 6.92 (d, 1H, J=8Hz, C₇-H), 8.12 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C₈-H), 7.64-6.82 (m, 2H, C_{3,4}-H), 7.81 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C_{6'}-H), 2.5 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH₂).

Other compounds of the series were prepared similarly and the results are shown in Table 2.

Biological activity: The compounds were administered i.p. in albino mice of either sex in different doses and approximate LD₅₀ values were determined by conventional procedure⁸. The results given in Table 2 indicate that the compounds were relatively nontoxic because their LD₅₀ values are quite high.

The anticonvulsant activity of V against pentylene tetrazole induced seizures was determined in mice⁹. The protection ability against pentylene tetrazol induced seizures ranged from 20-70% (Table 2). Maximum protection was observed in compound II₀ and minimum protection in compound II_r. These results possibly indicate that the introduction of nucleophile in phenyl ring at position 2 reduced its protecting ability, while introduction of electrophile enhanced its activity.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF 2-PHENOXYMETHYL-8-N-SUBSTITUTED AMINO CARBONYL METHYL-8-SUBSTITUTED-4(3H)-QUINAZOLONE (V)

Compound* No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	LD ₅₀	Anticonvulsant activity	
							Protection (%)	Mortality (%)
Ia	H	H	morpholinyl	110-112	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	1000	60	60
Ib	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	thiazolyl	139-140	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ SCl	1000	30	30
Ic	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	pyrrolidinyl	128-130	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	900	40	60
Id	H	H	pyrrolidinyl	120-121	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	980	50	50
Ie	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	cyclohexyl	145	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	1000	30	70
If	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	piperidinyl	105-107	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	850	20	80
Ig	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	thiazolyl	150-151	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	1000	60	40
Uh	H	H	thiazolyl	198-200	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S ₂	950	50	40
Ii	H	H	cyclohexyl	182	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	1000	40	60
Ij	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	morpholinyl	201	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	1000	60	40
Ik	H	H	thiazolyl	215	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ SI	980	50	40
Il	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	piperidinyl	195	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	1000	30	70
IIm	H	H	piperidinyl	170	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	900	40	50
IIn	H	H	morpholinyl	140	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₄ I	850	50	40

* The compounds were obtained in about 60-64% yields.

Elemental analysis of C, H and N were obtained within $\pm 0.4\%$.

Ib.	NMR (CDCl ₃) δ ppm : 8.33 (s, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₈ -H), 7.63-6.85 (m, 2H, C ₆₋₇ -H), 7.83 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 8.25 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₂ -H), 7.60-6.82 (m, 2H, C ₃₋₄ -H), 7.80 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).
Ig.	8.30 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 7.61-6.84 (m, 2H, C ₆₋₇ -H), 7.83 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 8.13 (d, 1H, C ₂ -H), 7.4-6.82 (m, 2H, C ₃₋₄ -H), 7.80 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 2.5 (s, 3H, CH ₃), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).
Iii.	8.33 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 7.61-6.82 (m, 2H, C ₆₋₇ -H), 7.81 (d, 1H, J=7Hz, C ₅ -H), 2.72 (m, 5H, Arom), 3.88 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).
Iv.	7.75 (d, 1H, J=8Hz, C ₅ -H), 7.32 (t, 1H, J=8Hz, C ₆ -H), 6.93 (d, 1H, J=8Hz, C ₇ -H), 2.70 (m, 5H, Arom), 3.82 (t, 2H, J=6Hz, OCH ₂).

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Synthesis of 1,2,4-Oxadiazolines Having Antifungal Activity

MANGAT RAI and (Miss) BALJIT KAUR

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University,
Ludhiana-141 004

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Continuation of our work on the synthesis of new heterocyclic compounds^{1,2} having antifungal activity 1,2,4-oxadiazolines have been prepared by

the cycloaddition of benzonitrile oxide to 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines¹. The cycloaddition of benzonitrile oxide to 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines has been carried out at 0° using different solvents like ether, chloroform, etc. depending upon the solubility of the Schiff bases. Benzonitrile oxide was generated *in situ* by the reaction of bases like triethylamine or 14% sodium hydroxide on the hydroxamoyl chloride². A mixture of two products was obtained in each case. The major product has been found to be the cycloadduct (I) and the minor one is identified as dimer⁴ (II) of the nitrile oxide through its m.p. and m.m.p. The cycloadducts can have a structure either Ia or Ib.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	N% Found (Calcd.)
1.	H	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	7.75 (7.77)
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	81	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	7.52 (7.49)
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl	67	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	7.09 (7.10)
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	74	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	7.09 (7.10)
5.	<i>p</i> -Br	69	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ Br	6.39 (6.38)